

Language and the Law: Sentence Complexity in Ghana’s 1992 Constitution¹

George K. Frimpong², Selina Ewoenam Ahorsu³

Abstract

This paper investigates the language of Ghana’s 1992 Constitution at the level of the sentence. Using the register assumption that linguistic choices are influenced by the context of situation, we investigate the use of sentences and their immediate clause constituents in the 1992 Constitution of Ghana. The study is premised on two notions. In the first place, the constitution is a legal document put together by legal experts. However, its contents (duties, obligations, responsibilities, rights, etc.) are meant for citizens of variegated backgrounds. One is curious to know how these factors influence linguistic choices in the constitutional document? In all, 13 chapters covering 639 sentences were studied using quantitative and qualitative methods. We found that the complex sentence type (including the compound complex sentence) is the preferred choice in the constitutional data. We equally observed that this predominant sentence type favours the use of several finite and non-finite subordinate clause combinations (up to 26 subordinate clauses in a single sentence). We argue based on these findings that though the complex sentence and its multiple clause combinations enable the framers of the constitution achieve precision and clarity, they inhibit readability and comprehensibility. This has implications for register argumentation and the general assumption that the audience is one of the variables that influence linguistic choices.

119

Keywords

Constitutional language, Ghanaian legal language, register, sentence complexity, clause combination

¹ This paper is based on data used for Selina Ewoenam Ahorsu’s MPhil thesis which was presented to the University of Ghana and supervised by Prof. Tayo Lamidi and Dr. George K. Frimpong.

² University of Ghana, email: frimpong.kodie@gmail.com ORCID: 0000-0002-3395-042X

³ University of Ghana, email: selinaewoenam@gmail.com ORCID: 0009-0005-7213-2373

Introduction

Language is context-driven. Its use varies across different situational contexts. As a result, one encounters different kinds of text over the course of a normal day from conversations, newspaper stories and sermons, to political talk, prayers, lectures, newspaper editorials, among others. Ike compares the versatility of language (especially English) to the clothes we wear and to the chameleon. According to him,

...language is not only comparable to the clothes we wear, of which there are ones for different occasions, but also comparable to the animal, chameleon, which changes colour with every environment. Like the chameleon, with its innumerable colours, English does not only have regional, social and functional varieties; it also has varieties for specific purposes. Thus, English has a variety for law, engineering, business, journalism, science and technology, religion etc. which are distinct from each other due to their peculiar linguistic choices and style (Ike, 2002, p. 7).

Some of the “peculiar linguistic choices” that differentiate ESP varieties include the grammar, vocabulary, structural and rhetorical organization. And so, the language of the law, we argue in this paper, differs from the other functional varieties of language such as the language of religion, the media and of business, etc. in the ways lexico-grammatical choices – especially grammatical structures such as the sentence and the clause – are made.

According to Hiltunen (1990), the following three kinds of legal texts exist: academic texts on law, legislative or statutory writings and juridical texts. While the academic texts on law include academic research found in legal textbooks, journals, etc., the juridical texts include language used in court proceedings, judgements, law reports, etc. The legislative writings, on the other hand, include constitutions, acts of parliament, contracts, treaties, etc. Among these, the constitution is considered the highest law of a nation, which describes the principles and processes of governance of that nation and the fundamental rights that its citizens are expected to enjoy.

According to the International Institute for Democratic and Electoral Assistance (IIDEA) (2014: 1), every constitution has the role of defining the rights and duties of citizens, expressing the identity and values of a national community, establishing and regulating political institutions, and prescribing the powers that the various layers of government have and how they are expected to expend those powers (IIDEA, 2014). The Constitution also declares and defines the fundamental principles and assumptions that govern the state, as well as where its sovereignty lies, among others (IIDEA, 2014). Ghana's *1992 Constitution*, for instance, states that “The Sovereignty of Ghana resides in the people of Ghana in whose name and for whose welfare the powers of government are to be exercised in the manner and within the limits laid down in the Constitution” (Ghana, 1992, p. 1). Thus, the Constitution, apart from being a legal instrument, is also a social declaration which expresses clearly the shared values and ideals of a people, and a political instrument which prescribes how state institutions are to be constituted and how these institutions are expected to expend the powers that they have (Lutz, 2006). This is why it is considered the highest law of nations or states. Recognising the enormous role that the constitution plays in the life of a nation and of its citizens and institutions, its contents need to be

clearly communicated in order that its demands can be clearly carried out or adhered to as required. It is, therefore, important that language use in the Constitution appropriately correspond to the communicative function of the Constitution.

Schauer (1982) is of the view that just as language of legal texts differs from other varieties of language, constitutional language may also have its unique features compared with the language of other legal texts. Being a highly formal written text, it is expected that the construction of the Constitution would be done with greater precision and a greater degree of ‘preproduction planning’ (Ochs, 1979). As such, the linguistic structures which found their way into the finished text of a Constitution would have been carefully thought through, having in mind the communicative function and the general situational context of the text.

In spite of the enormous importance of the Constitution in the affairs of a nation, not much work has been done on the language of the constitution especially relating it to its situational context. To the best of our knowledge, not much linguistic work on the *1992 Constitution of Ghana* exists. The scanty research available on legal language in general (Mellinkoff, 1963; Wydick, 1998; Tiersma, 1999; Wiredu, 2014) has found that legal English is full of lengthy, complex and unusual sentence structures. Many of these studies have argued that the complexity of sentences in legal texts is necessary for avoiding ambiguity (Wiredu, 2014). Others, however, admit that the quest to achieve clarity with lengthy and complex sentences rather ends up in creating ambiguity (Ufot, 2013). This paper focuses on the language of Ghana’s *1992 Constitution*. Limiting ourselves to sentence types and the internal clause constituents of dominant sentence types, we seek to relate language use to its situational context.

1. Constitutional language

As has been stated above, constitutions are highly formal written texts whose construction is supposedly done with greater precision and planning (Ochs, 1979). In his 1982 work, *An Essay on Constitutional Language*, in which he explores the way in which “the conventions of language affect constitutional theory”, Schauer argues that “constitutional language acts as a significant restraint on constitutional decision ...” (p. 799). He observes:

... the Constitution’s words are as different as they are special. To construe its language literally or too much like the language of a conventional statute would be both unrealistic and inconsistent with its deeper purposes (Schauer, 1982, p. 801)

The idea is that constitutional language is largely indeterminate and it is aimed at getting the *users* to think in different ways. For Post (1990, p. 14), “...the words of the Constitution appear to speak for themselves” in which case the Constitution would not need to be given any special interpretation before its demands are carried out. This suggests that the language of the Constitution is largely self-explanatory. Banfield, however, believes that vagueness of language is one feature of constitutional language which incidentally is not perceived until constitutional interpretation is sought (Banfield,

2014). Endicott (2000) identifies *lexical (semantic)* and *syntactic ambiguities* as the two main sources of vagueness and ambiguity in the language of legal documents. He explains that when a number of vague and ambiguous words combine into vague or ambiguous phrases and sentences, the combination usually results in more complexities. These complexities (linguistic ambiguities) in the Constitution may result in a varying number of opinions on certain laws which may in turn open the law up for any number of possible interpretations.

According to Ufot (2013, p. 630), legal drafters “employ sentences which are complicated with a myriad of qualifying subordinate clauses and phrases as well as excessive repetition”. He believes that the reliance on qualifying structures makes the sentences that we find in legal documents “jerky and unwieldy and often unintelligible to the general public” (Ufot, 2013, p. 630). The reasoning behind the piling up of structures into sentences in legal texts was to avoid ambiguity as well as “frustrate the possibility of loopholes which may be exploited by other lawyers or judges” (Ufot, 2013, p. 630). This decision, however, paradoxically results in the very ambiguity that was to be avoided as the complex structures end up interfering with intelligibility and communication (Ufot).

2. Previous studies on Ghanaian legal language

Not much work exists in the Ghanaian linguistic literature on the grammar of legal language. Apart from Wiredu’s study which examines the complex sentence in law reports, which aimed to establish the correlation between linguistic choices and the situational context of law reports, the other known linguistic research on legal language in the literature of Ghanaian linguistics has inclined towards critical discourse analysis and semantics by investigating courtroom cross-examination in terms of how these questions reflect unequal power relations (Ahiale, 2011; Edu-Buandoh & Ahiale, 2012) and of the ambiguity associated with contractual documents (Amoako-Atta, 1998) as a result of the use of modal verbs. One observes, equally, that there seems to be no known research on the language of Ghana’s *1992 Constitution* despite the fact that language is very crucial to its construction and interpretation.

In Amoako-Atta’s (1998) study, contractual documents (insurance policy documents) are investigated to ascertain ambiguities that the use of modal verbs occasion in these legal documents. He observes that modal verbs are a major source of the ambiguities in insurance documents. These modal ambiguities, Amoako-Atta argues, lead to difficulty in understanding insurance contracts.

Ahiale (2011) and Edu-Buandoh and Ahiale’s (2013) works on Ghanaian courtroom cross examination are examples of research on spoken legal texts. These studies investigate the use of questioning as an “elicitation strategy” by lawyers to cross examine their witnesses and defendants in order to determine their ideological implications. Using the “three-tier model of Critical Discourse Analysis” by Fairclough (1995), these studies observed that questions were used in Ghanaian courtrooms not just to seek for information but more importantly to entrench a number of ideological positions including showing power

differentiation, constraining defendants and witnesses, luring respondents into implicating themselves, manipulating defendants/witnesses to accept contrary positions and burdens (Ahialey 2011; Edu-Buandoh and Ahialey 2013).

Wiredu’s (2014) study is similar to our study in its focus on the complex sentence, though his investigation is on legal reports of Ghana’s Supreme Court decisions published in the *Daily Graphic* in 2011 and 2012. Among other things, Wiredu observes that the Ghanaian legal reports are replete with hypotactic clausal relations in the dominant complex sentences of this legal register. He argues, based on these observations, that, perhaps, the communicative purpose of legal reports to avoid ambiguity and to make the texts clear and precise motivates the dominance of this clause combining strategy. Wiredu’s findings apparently confirm the claims in the literature that legal language in general is complex (Vystrcilova, 2000; Shitu, 2011) and that this complexity is aimed at achieving precision, clarity, all-inclusiveness and unambiguousness.

The evidence is clear that the debate has begun about the nature of legal language in Ghanaian linguistics. That is, the scanty research in this area has covered a limited data and theoretical scope. What this means is that there is the need for more work in this area to make the debates and arguments complete. This should be composite in nature to encompass the broader spectrum of the entire scope of legal discourse and to embrace a variety of linguistic theorization. That is why this study is significant. Its focus on Ghana’s *1992 Constitution* is as timely as its stylistic/register focus is enlightening since it offers insights into the richness of the sociological indices within the stylistic variations of Ghanaian English (Wiredu, 2012).

3. Legal texts and grammatical/syntactic features

One conspicuous linguistic mark of legal documents has been their heavy reliance on complex linguistic structures such as multiple dependent clauses per sentence, complex phrase structures, excessive repetition, nominalization, passive constructions, unique determiners, impersonality, negatives, winding sentences, etc. (Danet, 1985; Ufot, 2013). Danet (1985: 281), for instance, explains this linguistic complexity of legal texts in the following

syntactic features are probably more distinctive of legal English than are lexical ones, and certainly account for more of the difficulties of lay persons in comprehending it.

Khan and Khan (Khan & Khan, 2015) make the observation more specific using textual evidence. To them, what makes legal documents particularly complex is the tendency for a single sentence in the legal register to take the space of an entire paragraph (Khan and Khan 2015). Frimpong (2018) makes a similar observation about newspaper editorial texts which have single sentences making up entire paragraphs. The difference, however, is perhaps in the degree of embedding in the sense that whereas the editorials Frimpong studied used a maximum of 8 dependent clauses per sentence, legal documents are noted to take up to 20 dependent clauses per sentence (Wiredu 2012). But precedent to these

studies is an earlier work (Gustafsson, 1975) whose quantitative methodological approach offers a quantificational detail to the argument. Gustafsson measured the average length of sentences in legal texts and observed that his legal texts had about 55 words per sentence, two times more than an average sentence length in scientific texts.

A study that is similar to the current study in terms of data focus is Bhatia (1994). His study of legislative or statutory legal writings supports the claim that legal discourse is structurally complex. He notes that though statutory writings are meant to be read by citizens, lawyers and judges usually have to read and interpret their contents to ordinary citizens due to their structural elaboration (Bhatia, 1994, pp. 141-144). Focusing longitudinally on one statutory writing, the *1992 Constitution of Ghana*, we probe to ascertain the nature of the structural elaboration of this type of legal discourse by unpacking the complex sentences and their clause combining properties in this constitutional data. To this end, we aim at revealing how language works in a legal text (the constitution) and how it “serves to constrain, if not determine interpretation” of these texts (Bex, 1996, p. 109). This is because, according to Akmajian (1995, p. 229) sentences with different structures, as is the case with legal texts, often have different communicative functions. Together with the sentence types, we investigate the immediate internal constituents, the clause, with the hope of contributing to the discussions in this area from a multilingual second language context.

4. The textual data and sampling

The primary data for this study is the *1992 Constitution of Ghana*. The choice of this formal written register is a convenient one. As a written document, its accessibility is guaranteed. Besides, we deem the constitution of Ghana as an important document of the land which must be explored from various perspectives. The effort at exploring it from multiple perspectives, we hope, will inform its review and perhaps also inspire the Ghanaian public to own and read this important document of their country.

In all, there are twenty-six chapters in this *1992 Constitution*, in addition to a preamble and two preliminary schedules. For the purpose of this study, thirteen chapters were sampled using *purposive sampling* technique, an approach which involves deliberately hand-picking supposedly typical or interesting cases or items from the population for investigation (Blaxter, Hughes, & Tight, 2017, p. 170). In selecting half of the entire document, one is hoping to cover a representative sample and a wide range of sentences. Besides, as argued by Biber and Conrad (2009), one does not need an entire text (and for that matter an entire document) for register analysis because

Registers can be identified and described based on analysis of either complete texts or a collection of text excerpts. This is because the linguistic component of a register analysis requires identification of the pervasive linguistic features in the variety: linguistic characteristics that might occur in any variety but are much more common in the target register. It is these pervasive linguistic features that are clearly functional... (Biber & Conrad, 2009, p. 6).

Moreover, the 13 chapters were purposively selected to cover three key thematic areas:

- The laws of Ghana: chapters 1, 4 and 25;
- The rights, privileges and freedoms of citizens: chapters 3, 5, 7, 12 and 21
- Governance and leadership: chapters 8, 9, 11 and 24.

Consideration was also given to the length of chapters (in terms of the total number of sentences) in order to have a fair representation of both long and short chapters. In this regard, chapters with more than 50 sentences were classified as long and those less than 50 sentences were classified as short⁴. Based on this principle, we identified chapters (5), (7), (8), (10) and (11) as long chapters all of which were sampled together with 8 short chapters for this study. Table 1 below provides a list of the chapters investigated and the number of sentences in each of the chapters.

Table 1. The thirteen sampled chapters

Chapters	Title	Number of Sentences
1	The Constitution	14
3	Citizenship	21
4	The Laws of Ghana	7
5	The Fundamental Human Rights and Freedoms	107
7	The Representation of the People	50
8	The Executive	120
9	The Council of State	28
10	The Legislature	95
11	The Judiciary	118
12	Freedom and Jurisprudence of the Media	18
21	Lands and Natural Resources	36
24	Code of Conduct for Public Officers	12
25	Amendment of the Constitution	13

These thirteen chapters cover 186 Articles and 639 Clauses in the *1992 Constitution*.

5. Analytical methodology

In order to be able to examine the distribution of sentence and clause patterns (which involve quantifying the particular types that are used in the 1992 constitution) and their interpretational values in the context of the text under study, both qualitative and

⁴ Note, however, that the selection based on the thematic areas overrides selection based on length.

quantitative approaches were adopted. According to Phakiti (2014), this mixed-method approach is appropriate because it enables the researcher “to combine the strengths of both the quantitative and the qualitative methods to gain a greater understanding of the influences of independent variables” (p.144). The quantitative analysis is employed because it satisfies the basic requirement of the register theory (Biber & Conrad, 2009) to conduct quantitative analysis of the linguistic features to identify the features that are pervasive. According to Giménez-Moreno and Skorczynskab (2013), effective register analysis needs to be quantitative in nature since the distribution of language items has functional implications for a given register. The next step of the analysis (the qualitative analysis) fulfils the need to interpret the functional relationship that exists between the linguistic features and the situational and communicative characteristics (Biber & Conrad, 2009). Thus, the qualitative analysis answers the question ‘why’.

6. Distribution of sentences

The classification of the unit of the sentence is done from both structural and functional perspectives. From these two perspectives, the sentence is described based on the supposed intention behind its use and the nature of its internal clause constituents (Frimpong, 2018).

6.1. The functional sentence types

According to this classification, sentences are grouped into declarative, interrogative, imperative and exclamative subtypes (Quirk, Greenbaum, Leech, & Svartvik, 1985; Frimpong, 2018). The total number of sentences examined in the individual chapters ranges from 7 to 120; the shortest chapter in the data in terms of the number of sentences being chapter four (*The Laws of Ghana*) and the longest being chapter eight (*the Executive*). It is important to note that the data tilted towards one functional category (the declarative sentence) and since there was no evidence of the use of the imperative, interrogative and exclamative sentences in the data, the discussion and analysis focused on the declarative sentence type. Table 2 below presents the attestations of the functional sentence types across the chapters. The percentages are computed for the total number of functional sentence types across the 13 chapters sampled for this study.

Table 2: Distribution of functional sentence types across chapters

Sentence Type	Frequency	Percentage
Declarative	639	100
Interrogative	0	0
Imperative	0	0
Exclamative	0	0
Total	639	100

The absolute dominance of the declarative sentence type as captured in Table 2 above confirms Shitu’s (2011) observation in her investigation of Nigerian legal texts that the language of legal texts is solely made up of complete sentences which make statements. This observation further confirms Wiredu’s (2014) observation that legal documents are the domain of the declarative sentence. Examples of declarative sentences used in our constitutional data are given below.

1. Parliament may make provision for the renunciation by any person of his citizenship of Ghana.
2. The existing law shall, except as otherwise provided in clause (1) of this article, comprise the written and unwritten laws of Ghana as they existed immediately before the coming into force of this Constitution, and any Act, Decree, law or statutory instrument issued or made before that date, which is to come into force on or after that date.

The dominance of the declarative sentence type is not as significant as the complete absence of the other sentence types (interrogative, imperative and exclamative types). Normally, the declarative sentence is more frequent than any other functional type across several registers (Frimpong, 2018; Frimpong, 2019; Wiredu, 2012). The observation, however, is that, as Frimpong (2018; 2019) and Wiredu (2012) observe, the other functional sentence types are also attested, though minimally so, in some other registers. This is why their total absence in the constitutional register is a cause for concern and which may be used to qualify constitutional language.

An observation one makes about the type of declarative sentences prevalent in our constitutional data is the complexity of their structure as exemplified in sentence (2) above. The complexity of these declarative sentences makes an exploration of the internal structural make up of sentences in the constitutional data a worthy enterprise which we have done in the next section below.

5.2. The structural sentence types

Structurally, sentences are classified based on the number and types of clauses that make them up (Frimpong, 2019). The traditional classification of sentences from this perspective gives us the simple, compound, complex and compound-complex sentences (Quirk, Greenbaum, Leech, & Svartvik, 1985; Rozakis, 2003). We observed from the data that the preferred structural sentence pattern is the type that is made up of one independent clause and one or more subordinate clauses, which in this case, is the complex sentence. The attestations of the structural sentence types are presented in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Distribution of structural sentence types

Types	Frequency	Percentage
Simple	85	13.0
Compound	22	3.0
Complex	413	65.0
Comp-cplx	119	19.0
Total	639	100.00

Key: Comp-cplx (Compound-complex)

From Table 3 above, it is apparent that the complex sentence is the preferred type. More than 60% (i.e. 65% (n=413)) of the total number of sentences are complex. This is followed by the compound-complex sentence which constitutes 19% (n= 119) of the total number of sentences. The compound complex sentence itself is a form of complex sentence since it has in it a complex sentence. Below are some examples of the complex and compound-complex sentences found in the data.

3. The notice referred to in clause (2) of this article shall be accompanied by a statement in writing setting out in detail the facts, supported by the necessary documents, on which it is claimed that the conduct or the physical or mental capacity of the President be investigated for the purposes of his removal from office. (Complex sentence)
4. Subject to clause (5) of this article, the Chief Justice shall, by constitutional instrument, immediately convene a tribunal consisting of the Chief Justice as Chairman and the four most senior Justices of the Supreme Court and the tribunal shall inquire, in camera, whether there is a prima facie case for the removal of the President. (Comp-cplx)

128

Thus, there is preference for sentence types which contain subordinate clauses at the expense of sentences which have either multiple independent clauses or a single clause. Together, both the complex and compound-complex sentences constitute 85% of the sentences in the constitution. The remaining types, the simple and compound sentences represent 16% (13% and 3% respectively) of the sentences in our constitutional data.

The first noteworthy observation about these findings is that though legal documents are noted to be structurally complex, our data suggests that the complexity of the *1992 Constitution of Ghana* does not reflect an absolute reliance on complex sentences (at least some 16% of sentences are non-complex sentences). Elsewhere, (2014) has made a similar finding in his study of legal reports which formed the basis for his argument that legal language is often considered complex and difficult to understand because writers use specific linguistic items to make the language as precise, clear and unambiguous as possible. The goal of achieving unambiguous communication is among the motivations for structural repetition, apposition, complementation, restatement, etc. – functions performed by clause complexing. (2012) has also argued that a complex sentence is a suitable choice for information packaging as it allows for all the senses of the information that need to be passed to be properly expressed.

7. Distribution of dependent clauses

As the complex and compound complex sentences are the dominant sentence types, we explored closely the immediate internal structure of these dominant structural sentences. This involved ascertaining the number of dependent clauses that make up the complex and compound complex sentence types (referred to collectively as COMPLEX sentence, henceforth).

7.1. Number of clauses per COMPLEX sentence

An investigation of the dependent clauses in the (532) COMPLEX sentences in the constitutional data reveals that there are (1640) dependent clauses which are distributed in varying numbers in their sentences as captured in Table 4 below.

Table 4: Number of dependent clauses per sentence

Types	No. of Sentences	%	No. of Dep Clauses
Sentences with 1 Dep. Clauses	168	31.6	168
Sentences with 2 Dep. Clauses	122	22.9	244
Sentences with 3 Dep. Clauses	88	16.5	264
Sentences with 4 Dep. Clauses	52	9.8	208
Sentences with 5 Dep. Clauses	32	6.0	160
Sentences with 6 Dep. Clauses	25	4.7	150
Sentences with 7 Dep. Clauses	10	1.9	70
Sentences with 8 Dep. Clauses	10	1.9	80
Sentences with 9 Dep. Clauses	7	1.3	63
Sentences with 10 Dep. Clauses	5	0.9	50
Sentences with 11 Dep. Clauses	6	1.1	66
Sentences with 12 Dep. Clauses	2	0.4	24
Sentences with 14 Dep. Clauses	1	0.2	14
Sentences with 17 Dep. Clauses	1	0.2	17
Sentences with 18 Dep. Clauses	2	0.4	36
Sentences with 26 Dep. Clauses	1	0.2	26
Total	532	100.0	1640

According to Bex (1996, p. 95), “texts orient themselves to readers in particular ways, and organize their information in ways appropriate” to communicative function and the situational context of the given register. It is our argument in this paper then that in constructing a text, attention is paid to selecting language elements which are capable of reflecting the purpose of the text. Thus, we hold the view that the framers of the constitution

of Ghana made grammatical choices carefully, mindful of ideologies, principles, duties, rights, etc. that had to be captured in it. Table 4 above indicates that the (1640) dependent clauses which were realised from (532) COMPLEX sentences are distributed in the individual sentences in varying numbers, with each of the sentences having between (1) and (26) dependent clauses. Sentences (5), (6) and (7) below, for instance, contain (1), (6) and (10) subordinate clauses, respectively. More examples including the sentence with the highest number of subordinate clauses are discussed below.

5. Every person *who*, on the coming into force of this Constitution, *is a citizen of Ghana by law* shall continue to be a citizen of Ghana. (COMPLEX sentence with 1 dependent clause)
6. A woman *married to a man who is a citizen of Ghana* or a man *married to a woman who is a citizen of Ghana* may, upon *making an application* in the manner *prescribed by Parliament*, be registered as a citizen of Ghana. (COMPLEX sentence with 6 dependent clauses)
7. A person *who becomes a citizen of Ghana* by registration and immediately after the day *on which he becomes a citizen of Ghana is also a citizen of some other country*, shall cease to be a citizen of Ghana *unless he has renounced his citizenship of that other country, taken the oath of allegiance specified in the Second Schedule to this Constitution and made and registered such declaration of his intentions concerning residence* as may be prescribed by law, or *unless he has obtained an extension of time for taking those steps and the extended period has not expired*. (COMPLEX sentence with 10 dependent clauses)

The distribution of dependent clauses in the sentences of our constitutional data is very characteristic of the constitutional register in the sense that not many registers have up to (26) dependent clauses in their sentences. Frimpong (2018), for instance, observes a maximum of (8) subordinate clauses per sentence in his exploration of newspaper editorials. Wiredu's (2014) exploration of legal reports identified a maximum of (20) dependent clauses per sentence. While this observation confirms the claim in the literature that the use of long and complex sentences, as well as multiple subordinating structures is very characteristic of legal English (Shitu 2011; Khan and Khan 2015), it also indicates that there are sub-varieties of the legal register based on levels of complexity. In this regard, the constitutional register may be placed among the most complex legal registers.

7.2. Finite and non-finite dependent clauses

An attempt was made at investigating the use of finite and non-finite dependent clauses in our constitutional data. We wonder whether the communicative purpose of legal texts to be explicit and precise will predispose it towards finite or non-finite clauses. We report in Table 6 below how the finite and non-finite dependent clauses are distributed in the data.

Table 6: Distribution of finite/ non-finite dependent clauses

Type	Frequency	Percentage
Finite	788	48.05
Non-finite	852	51.95
Total	1640	100

From Table 6, we observe that there are more non-finite clauses than finite clauses in the constitutional data, though the difference is not so much. The non-finite clauses constitute 51.95% (n=852) of the (1640) dependent clauses and the remaining 48.05% (n= 788) are finite.

8. Discussion of results

The attempt in this qualitative interpretation was to determine the functional motivations behind the choices of sentence and clause patterns in the data (Biber & Conrad, 2009, p. 64). This involved matching the distributional patterns of these grammatical units with the situational context of a constitution. We have already argued from register perspective that the distribution of linguistic features in a register is functionally motivated (Biber & Conrad, 2009). The basic assumption of the register theory is that the choices of linguistic items in constructing or composing texts are not arbitrarily done. Rather, these choices are influenced by the context within which the text is produced (Biber & Conrad, 2009). In the ensuing paragraphs we interrogate and interpret the pervasive sentence and clause types in Ghana’s 1992 Constitution.

8.1. The use of the declarative sentence

Our observation that the data consists of functional sentence types which are solely declarative is very significant. The absolute reliance on the declarative form in the constitution raises such questions as: why have the declarative sentences dominated the data and how significant are they with reference to the situational characteristics and communicative purpose of the constitution?

Firstly, and as already indicated above, Ghana’s *1992 Constitution* is a more specified kind of written legal text according to which Ghana as a country is governed; it is the supreme law of the nation and it enjoys a great sense of heightened dignity and authority and; a lot of planning went into its production. The ideas and principles in the *1992 Constitution* were collated through a series of regional fora which were organized across the country from the mid 1990 by the National Commission for Democracy (NCD) (Frempong, 2007, p. 19). The ideas received during the regional fora were compiled by a team of experts and placed before a Consultative Assembly which deliberated on it before the compilation was approved after being subjected to a referendum on April 9, 1992. It is important to note that through all these processes, the drafters/writers had the opportunity to revise, edit, delete and add until the document was able to convey exactly what they intended

it to convey. This makes the Constitution a highly formal and well-planned written text, whose content cannot easily be altered even though there are provisions for amendment. It is expected then that sentence types used will consist of only complete sentences that are able to fully carry the message of the constitution across to readers (Shitu, 2011). The declarative sentence therefore appears to be the most suitable for conveying the message of the Constitution.

Again, we have established that the main communicative purpose of a nation's constitution is to teach the law to its citizens, inform them about their rights and privileges as well as impose obligations on them. Being the supreme law of the land, the content of all constitutions and for that matter Ghana's *1992 Constitution* is expected to be mandatory and binding on the citizens as well as residents of the land (Lutz, 2006; IIDEA, 2014). These functions are usually performed by expressing the ideas or information about the legal, political and social considerations in clear and explicit manners, perhaps in order to avoid misunderstandings and misrepresentations. In doing so, statements are made concerning what constitutes the law, the rights, privileges, and freedoms as well as the obligations of the citizens, and the role and duties of elected leadership and state institutions. We can thus conclude that the declarative form with its discourse function to inform is well suited for this function. Its overwhelming choice can therefore be said to be appropriate.

Furthermore, due to the fact that the relationship that exists between the writers (experts) and the readers (largely non-experts) is non-interactive in nature because the writer(s) are not physically present and easily accessible to the readers, the content of the Constitution needs to be presented in a way that will provide all the needed information the readers can easily relate to. In other words, readers need to be able to understand the legal, social and political matters (Lutz, 2006, pp. 16-17) that the Constitution contains. As has been argued by Panther and Köpcke (2008), two main natural consequences of a declarative sentence are for the hearer to get informed or get pushed into taking some action. Thus, the two-way purpose of the constitution to teach the law by providing information as well as to direct and impose obligations and restrictions are appropriately achieved with the declarative sentence. Generally, chapters 1 (*The Constitution*), 4 (*The Laws of Ghana*), and 25 (*Amendment of the Constitution*), "express the identity and values of the national community", define where its sovereignty lies and as well present the laid down procedures which must be followed to effect changes in these *Laws* where there is the need to do so (IIDEA, 2014). Chapter one of the Constitution, for instance, talks about the power of the constitution, its enforcement and its defence. The first two sentences in chapter one, which are grouped under the sub-title *Supremacy of the Constitution*, for instance, are informative (declarative, for that matter). That is, they define where the nation's sovereignty lies.

8. The Sovereignty of Ghana resides in the people of Ghana in whose name and for whose welfare the powers of government are to be exercised in the manner and within the limits laid down in this Constitution. (DECLARATIVE)
9. The Constitution shall be the supreme law of Ghana and any other law found to be inconsistent with any provision of this Constitution should, to the extent of the inconsistency, be void. (DECLARATIVE)

While sentence 8 informs the public that the supreme authority and absolute political power lies in the bosom of the nation’s people and the exercise of such power needs to be done within the dictates of the constitution, sentence 9 informs the public about the supremacy of the constitution and that any other law which does not draw from the constitution will be considered void. Both sentence 8 and 9 are declarative sentences used to perform a direct speech function of informing and stating facts. However, the declarative sentences under the subtitles, *Enforcement of the Constitution* and *Defence of the Constitution* are largely directive; an indirect speech function performed by the declarative sentence. The sentences below exemplify the indirect directive speech function of the declarative sentence.

10. Any person or group of persons to whom an order or direction is addressed under clause (2) of this article by the Supreme Court, shall duly obey and carry out the terms of the order or direction. (DECLARATIVE)
11. Parliament shall have no power to enact a law establishing a one-party state. (DECLARATIVE)
12. Any person who – (a) by himself or in concert with others by any violent or other unlawful means, suspends or overthrows or abrogates this Constitution or any part of it, or attempts to do any such act; or (b) aids and abets in any manner any person referred to in paragraph (a) of this clause; commits the offence of high treason and shall, upon conviction, be sentenced to suffer death. (DECLARATIVE)

Rather than merely making statements which convey information, these declarative sentences issue directives and impose obligations by prescribing what one can or cannot do even though they follow the subject-verb order. This function is made possible because though these sentences are declarative in structure, they have deontic modals (which are verbs of control) which express directivity.

In addition, Chapters 3 (*Citizenship*), 5 (*The Fundamental Human Rights and Freedoms*), 7 (*The Representation of the People*), 12 (*Freedom and Jurisprudence of the Media*), and 21 (*Lands and Natural Resources*) also focus on the rights, privileges and freedoms that citizens (and/or residents) as well as institutions are entitled to under the 1992 Constitution. The declarative sentences in these chapters are not merely informative. They are used tentatively to perform functions that are associated with the imperative sentence. For instance, Chapter 5, which focuses on explaining the rights, privileges and freedoms that citizens (and/or residents) are entitled to under the constitution gives power to the citizenry to demand to be treated fairly by everyone in different situations. It also regulates the manner in which individuals and institutions treat the citizens and/or residents of the country. One’s ignorance of the privileges and freedoms one is entitled to may deny one the opportunity to access and enjoy these rights. In addition, the failure of individuals and institutions to uphold and respect the rights that others are entitled to may constitute an offence under the constitution. It seems obvious then that the declarative sentence, with its underlying directive focus is appropriate in fulfilling the purpose of this chapter because its use is most suited for both informing citizens about their rights and privileges and imposing obligations as well. The sentences below are evidentiary:

13. The fundamental human rights and freedoms enshrined in this chapter shall be respected and upheld by the Executive, Legislature and Judiciary and all other

organs of government and its agencies and, where applicable to them, by all natural and legal persons in Ghana, and shall be enforceable by the Courts as provided for in this Constitution. (DECLARATIVE)

14. Every person in Ghana, whatever his race, place of origin, political opinion, colour, religion, creed or gender shall be entitled to the fundamental human rights and freedoms of the individual contained in this Chapter but subject to respect for the rights and freedoms of others and for the public interest. (DECLARATIVE).

These sentences appear to give information that every individual has rights. Yet, again, it is evident that rather than merely informing, they are prescriptive and restrictive in nature. In other words, these and all the other sentences in chapter five prescribe what one's rights are as well as how these rights are to be protected, respected and exercised.

Furthermore, chapters 8 (*the Executive*), 9 (*the Council of State*), 10 (*the Legislature*), 11 (*the Judiciary*), and 24 (*Code of Conduct for Public Officers*) provide information on leadership and governance. They also establish and regulate political institutions (IIDEA, 2014, p. 2). In terms of their communicative function, these chapters direct, prescribe and proscribe the duties and roles of individuals and institutions that are charged with responsibilities of the state. Chapter 8, for instance, which is titled *The Executive* talks about who qualifies to be a president or vice president, the processes by which one ascends those positions, what the president can and cannot do while serving as president, as well as the circumstances under which a vice president can succeed the president and the procedures through which a president can be removed from office. Detailed information is also provided on who qualifies to be a Minister of State, Attorney General and how state institutions like the National Security Council and the National Development Planning Commission are supposed to be composed and the functions they have. The guidelines and procedures stipulated in the chapter are obligatory since they direct, prescribe and proscribe. Let us examine the sentences below.

15. The President shall take precedence over all other persons in Ghana; and in descending order, the Vice-President, the Speaker of Parliament and the Chief Justice, shall take precedence over all other persons in Ghana (DECLARATIVE)
16. The President shall not leave Ghana without prior notification in writing, signed by him and addressed to the Speaker of Parliament (DECLARATIVE)
17. The Electoral Commission shall, by constitutional instrument, make regulations for the purpose of giving effect to article 63 of this Constitution (DECLARATIVE)

These sentences are declarative and, like the others above, they both inform and direct. One can say that the general purpose of the Constitution, as well as the specific purposes of each of the chapters, is to teach the law. It does this through disseminating information in a manner as “binding on everyone in the state” as possible (IIDEA, 2014, p. 1). This explains the over reliance on the declarative as the preferred sentence type in the data. It may be argued that the choice of the declarative offers the drafters/writers of the Constitution the opportunity to tone down the obvious force that an imperative sentence would have carried had it been used.

Thus, given the key situational characteristics (Biber & Conrad, 2009) of the constitution – the participants (addressors and addressees) and the relationship that exists between them, the channel, the production process as well as its communicative purpose, it is the declarative sentence (with its directive focus) which appears the most suitable to express the information. That is, the constitution was written by experts to non-experts under circumstances that allowed for editing. Its communicative purpose is to inform the non-expert citizens very important policies rules and regulations and to impose duties and obligations on citizens and institutions. This is at the foundation of the uniqueness of the constitutional register which influences its preference for only declarative sentences.

8.2. The use of the complex sentence and clause combination as a linguistic strategy

As argued by Tiersma (1999), legal language was the preserve of experts who were knowledgeable in Latin, French and English. The desire of legal experts in the past to have monopoly over the interpretation of legal texts and the provision of legal services and the desire to preserve the language and justify their fees led to the use of unnecessarily long and complex sentences (Tiersma, 1999). The preference for long and winding sentences is also true of modern legal writing. This observation confirms the claims in the literature that the language of legal texts is complex (Vystrcilova, 2000; Endicott, 2000; Shitu, 2011; Ufot, 2013; Wiredu, 2014). This complexity is seen in the use of sentences which are made extremely long by multiple subordinate clauses for the purposes of information elaboration or expansion or information ranking.

As has been observed in Table 3 above, there is the predominant use of complex structures (i.e. complex and compound-complex sentences) in the data. These sentence types allow for piling up of information (Wiredu, 2012). That is, they allow for the integration of several propositions into a single grammatical unit. Unlike in the simple and compound sentences, information is arranged hierarchically in the complex and compound-complex sentences, giving more emphasis to the independent clause(s). A typical complex sentence in the data has the following form:

18. No penalty shall be imposed for a criminal offence that is severer in degree or description than the maximum penalty that could have been imposed for that offence at the time when it was committed (COMPLEX)

In terms of information ranking, the main clause is the highest. This is because it carries the main message, which is expressed in a complete thought for which reason it can stand alone as a complete sentence (Frimpong, 2017). This is followed by the adverbial clause, *when it was committed*. Though the adverbial clause cannot by itself express a complete thought, unlike the relative clause, it does not depend on a clause element. It relates, however, with the main clause from which it can be detached without affecting the grammar of the sentence (Greenbaum, 1996). The relative clause comes next in the rank. In this order of hierarchy, therefore, the clauses in sentence (18) can be diagrammed roughly as follows with the clause highest in rank at the top.

Figure 1: Clause hierarchy in complex sentence

A careful look at this clause hierarchy diagram reveals that the sentence diagrammed provides three pieces of information. The main idea which is expressed by the main clause is considered the most important. This is followed by the circumstantial information of time captured in the adverbial clause. The qualifying information which is expressed by the relative clauses, both of which are of equal rank, comes next because they operate as modifiers within noun phrases.

136

Similarly, sentence (19) below is made up of one independent clause and four dependent clauses which are combined through the process of subordination and arranged hierarchically.

19. A person who has made a contemporaneous report of the proceedings in Parliament, including a statement which has been the subject of an inquiry under clause (2) of this article, shall publish the apology referred to in clause (3) of this article or the suspension or the apology referred to in clause (4) of this article with the same prominence as he published the first report (COMPLEX)

The main clause in the sentence is *A person...shall publish the apology ...* and it is the most important clause in the sentence. However, it is not quite clear until the reader is made aware of who shall publish the apology, 'why' the apology is needed, under what circumstances or conditions the apology should be rendered or published, among other necessary pieces of information; and these are what the dependent clauses listed below (in order of appearance) are meant for.

- who has made a contemporaneous report of the proceedings in Parliament, including a statement
- which has been the subject of an inquiry under clause (2) of this article
- referred to in clause (3) of this article or the suspension or the apology

- referred to in clause (4) of this article with the same prominence
- as he published the first report.

Yet still, the message of this clause is not fully retrieved until the reader goes back to read clause (3) and (4) of the article as indicated in participial clauses, *referred to in clause (3)* and *referred to in clause (4)*. It appears that there is an effort to use multiple subordinate clauses to pile up information in this sentence and this pattern seems repetitive throughout the entire data perhaps for the purpose of avoiding ambiguity and/or doubt. Just like in sentence (18), the information that the individual clauses in sentence (19) carries is arranged hierarchically. Figure 2 below is illustrative.

Figure 2: Clause hierarchy in complex sentence 19

Note that there are four adjectival clauses in the sentence above; two relative clauses which are higher in rank than the participial clauses. As Payne (2011) argues, the relative clauses are higher in rank because they are full clauses whose verbs are tensed.

The complex sentence in the constitutional data can be very long, having as many as (26) subordinate clauses as illustrated by sentence (20) below.

20. A person shall not be qualified to be a member of Parliament if he – (a) owes allegiance to a country other than Ghana; or (b) has been adjudged or otherwise declared- (i) bankrupt under any law in force in Ghana and has not been discharged or (ii) to be of unsound mind or is detained as a criminal lunatic under any law in force in Ghana; or (c) has been convicted – (i) for high crime under this Constitution or high treason or treason or for an offence involving the security of the State, fraud, dishonesty or moral turpitude; or (ii) for any other offence punishable by death or by a sentence of not less than ten years; or (iii) for an offence relating to, or connected with election under a law in force in Ghana at any time; or (d) has been found by the report of a commission or a committee of inquiry to be incompetent to hold public office or is a person in respect of whom a commission or committee of inquiry has

• Key: S= Sentence boundary; Sb= Subject boundary; P= Predicate boundary; C= Complement

Figure 3: The constituent structure of sentence 20

DOI:

found that while being a public officer he acquired assets unlawfully or defrauded the State or mis-used or abused his office, or wilfully acted in a manner prejudicial to the interest of the State, and the findings have not been set aside on appeal or judicial review; or (e) is under sentence of death or other sentence of imprisonment imposed on him by any court; or (f) is not qualified to be registered as a voter under any law relating to public elections; or (g) is otherwise disqualified by a law in force at the time of the coming into force of this Constitution, not being inconsistent with a provision of this Constitution. (DECLARATIVE)

The main clause of this complex sentence is *A person shall not be qualified to be a member of Parliament*. The sentence also has multiple co-ordinated *if-clauses*, whose aims are to show the way in which the idea or proposition in the main clause is contingent on the fulfilment of the conditions expressed by these clauses. The nominal elements in these *if-clauses* are further post-modified by participial clauses. This sentence can be expressed, having numbered the dependent clauses, in this form:

A person shall not be qualified **(i) (ii) or (iii) and (iv) or (v) or (vi) or (vii)** for high crime under this Constitution or high treason or for an offence **(viii)** moral turpitude; or for any other offence ... or for an offence **(ix) or (x) (xi) (xii) or (xiii)**...a person **(xiv) (xv) :[that (xvii) he acquired assets unlawfully] or (xvi) or (xviii) or (xix) or (xx) ... imprisonment (xxi) or (xxii) (xviii) under any law (xxiv)or (xxv) (xxvi).**

The linear relationship between the clauses of this sentence can be roughly represented with brackets (see Figure 3 below) referred to as Nelson’s model (Irmawati & Hum, 2014) of constituent analysis.

The different layers of the brackets explain how nested the clauses are and they also reveal the relationship that exists between one clause and the other. For example, clauses (i), (iii), (iv), (v) and vi are coordinated by *or* and *and*. Similarly, clauses (xvi), (xviii), (xix), (xx) are also coordinated by *or*. However, clause ii is embedded in clause i and clauses xiv, xv and xvii are also embedded in clause xiii. This sentence is loaded with a lot of information; the main clause is followed by multiple subordinate structures which are providing additional information. Hierarchically, the clauses in this sentence can be arranged as follows:

Figure 4 above also shows the subordinate clauses arranged in order of hierarchy.

The compound-complex sentences in the data also share similar features with the complex sentences by having one or more subordinate clauses which provide different kinds of information necessary for understanding the message of the sentence. They differ, however, only for having more than one independent clause. Sentence (21) below is illustrative.

21. Where a member refuses to render an apology in accordance with clause (3) of this article, the Speaker shall suspend that member for the duration of the session of parliament in which the defamatory statement was made and a member so suspended shall lose his parliamentary privileges, immunities and remuneration, but they shall be restored to him if, at any time before the end of the session, he renders the apology as required by clause (3) of this article. (COMPOUND-COMPLEX)

Figure 4: Clause hierarchy in sentence 20

The main clauses that make up the sentence above are:

- the Speaker shall suspend that member for the duration of the session of parliament;
- a member so suspended shall lose his parliamentary privileges, immunities and remuneration; and
- they shall be restored to him

These independent clauses are coordinated by the use of “and” and “but”. The adverbial clause *where a member refuses* and the infinitival clause *to render an apology in accordance with clause (3) of this article*, both provide the reason for which the action in the first independent clause shall be carried out. The relative clause *in which the defamatory statement was made* post-modifies the noun, “parliament” in the first main clause whereas the other two subordinate clauses *if, at any time before the end of the session, he renders the apology* and *as required by clause (3) of this article* both provide the conditions under which the action in the third independent clause could get fulfilled. We have argued already that sentence complexity involves the use of subordinate clauses as a means of expanding the information structure (Bloor & Bloor, 2004) either in the nominal group or in the verbal group or as comments. The information provided by these individual clauses are ranked hierarchically, as illustrated in Figure 5 below.

The three independent clauses in sentence (21) above are grammatically equal in rank and so are deemed to contain information of equal status. The use of ‘and’ is an indication of an additive relationship extending the information already begun in the preceding independent clause while the use of ‘but’ suggests a contrastive relationship in which a piece of information is in contrast with another of equal importance (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014). Thus, while the independent clauses are employed to combine ‘similar’ ideas, the subordinate clauses are used to elaborate on the claims made in the independent clauses

Figure 5: Clause hierarchy in compound-complex sentence 21

(as in the relative clause), extend the reasoning behind those claims (as in the adverbial clauses) and complement the thought processes of a given claim (as in the nominal clause).

It is evident from the discussions above that the use of sentences with subordinate clauses has significant implications for the message of the texts in which they are employed. One would appreciate the fact that the reliance of Ghana’s 1992 Constitution on complex and compound-complex declarative sentences is due to its focus to feed its readers with a more detailed, elaborate and expansive information (Wiredu, 2012), while at the same time being restrictive, prescriptive and prohibitive (Ochs, 1979). It also seems obvious that using the independent clause alone in a writing situation without the relevant circumstantial and qualifying clauses may deny the reader of making complete meaning of the sentences. Besides, the explanations contained in these subordinate clauses prevent the situation where someone can interpret the constitution to his or her advantage. Unlike in an oral communication situation where the listener has the luxury of seeking further clarification, or making meaning due to contextual clues such as facial expression, intonational dynamics, etc., the written situation demands that every necessary piece of information that is required for understanding is provided to give support to the independent clauses. Thus, the subordinate clauses help in expanding and elaborating the main clause.

It can be said that this complex relationship between the clauses is enough to complicate meaning making. It is arguable that the use of multiple subordinate clauses (as in sentence (20) and the others above) is an indication that the reader would have “to store several bits of information in his memory” (Ufot, 2013, p. 629) in order to properly make meaning of the circumstances under which the dictates of the main clause or main clauses are to be understood, and reading it can be demanding. This observation finds support in (Mala, 2012), who observes that when used, the multiple dependent clauses make sentences in

text extremely complex which tend to interrupt the flow of the text by giving details about ideas and this puts considerable stress on the concentration of the reader. This situation is likely to result in information loss. The position of this study therefore is that text complexity at the structural level is both a necessity to the legal culture and a burden to the lay man.

8.3. The use of non-finite subordinate clauses

The dominance of non-finite subordinate clauses in the data is significant. We have established that the constitution's focus to integrate information motivates its choice of several finite and non-finite dependent clauses. However, the preference for non-finite dependent clauses is suitable for a highly formal text such as the 1992 Constitution of the Republic of Ghana. This observation is supported by Malá (2011; 2012) that formal written texts have the tendency of using non-finite structures at the expense of finite ones.

Again, it has been established above that non-finite clauses are suitable for information integration because they lack certain important grammatical features. As argued by Frimpong (2015), participial clauses such as the one in the phrase "a person *appointed to an office*" could become a finite clause, "who has been appointed to an office", with its subject and verb recovered. This implies that had more finite clauses been used, more words would have been involved in the sentence construction of the constitution whose contents are already labeled as complex and complicated, which would make it even bulkier. It is argued then that non-finite dependent clauses are more suitable for information integration.

Conclusion

This paper has argued that though Ghana's *1992 Constitution*, like all other constitutions, enshrines the rights and responsibilities of Ghanaians of all educational backgrounds, its language is very complex. Focusing on the dominant sentence types (the complex and its allied compound complex sentences) and their immediate constituent, the clause, we examined the nature of the structural complexity of the constitutional data. We found that the complex sentence types (including compound complex sentence) are the preferred choice in the constitutional data. This structural complexity, we note, promotes the use of a host of finite and non-finite subordinate clauses (up to (26) subordinate clauses). We have argued based on this observation that though these complex structures enable the framers of the constitution to stack related messages in a single sentence, its tendency to obfuscate the language of the constitution makes it difficult to read and understand. This means that though the constitution enshrines information meant for all Ghanaians, not all Ghanaians can read and understand it.

References

- Ahiale, H. (2011). *Elicitation and Response Strategies in Courtroom Cross examination: A Critical Discourse Analysis*. Cape Coast: University of Cape Coast.
- Akmajian, A. (1995). *Linguistics: An Introduction to Law and Communication*. Cambridge: MIT Press.
- Amoako-Atta, G. (1998). *Modality in Ghanaian Contractual Documents*. University of Cape Coast. Cape Coast: University of Cape Coast.
- Banfiled, C. (2014). *The Importance of Interpretation: How the Language of the Constitution Allows for Differing Opinions*. University of Tennessee. Tennessee: University of Tennessee .
- Bex, T. (1996). *Variety in written English*. London: Routledge.
- Bhatia, V. (1994). Cognitive Structuring in Legislative Provisions. In J. (. Gibbons, *Language and the Law* (pp. 136-155). Harlow: Longman Group.
- Biber, D., & Conrad, S. (2009). *Register, Genre and Style*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Blaxter, L., Hughes, C., & Tight, M. (2017). *How to Research*. England: Open University Press.
- Bloor, T., & Bloor, M. (2004). *The Functional Analysis of English*. London: Arnold.
- Danet, B. (1985). Legal Discourse. In V. D. (ed), *Handbook of Discourse Analysis* (Vol. Vol. 1, pp. 273-291). London: Academia Press.
- Edu-Buandoh, D., & Ahiale, H. (2012). Exploring the Ideological Implications of Questions In Elicitation In Courtroom Cross-Examination Discourse In Ghana. *Language, Dicourse & Society, Vol. 1*(No. 2), 11-30.
- Endicott, T. (2000). *Vagueness in Law*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Frempong, A. (2007). Constitution-Making and Constitutional Rule in Ghana. *CODESRIA Books*.
- Frimpong, G. K. (2015). *A Comparative Register Analysis of Editorials from Ghanaian and British Newspapers*. University of Ghana. Accra: University of Ghana.
- Frimpong, G. K. (2017). Subordination Across Ghanaian and British Newspaper Editorials: A register Perspective. *Ghana Journal of Linguistics, Vol. 6*(1), 72 – 115.
- Frimpong, G. K. (2018). The complex sentence across written genres from native and nonnative contexts; A corpus-based study. *SKASE Journal of Theoretical Linguistics, Vol. 15*(3), 185-203.
- Frimpong, G. K. (2019). Cross-dialectal similarity of registers: The case of the sentence across Ghanaian and British newspaper editorials. *SKASE Journal of Theoretical Linguistics, Vol. 16*(2), 104 -130.
- Ghana, R. o. (1992). *Constitution of the Republic of Ghana*. Ghana.
- Gimenez-Moreno, R., & Skorzynskab, H. (2013). Corpus Variation: A Field in need of an Update. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences, Vol. 95*, 402 – 408.
- Greenbaum, S. (1996). *The Oxford Grammar of English*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Gustafsson, M. (1975). *Binomial Expressions in Present-day English: A Syntactic and Semantic Study*. Turku: Turun Yliopisto.
- Halliday, M. A., & Matthiessen, C. (2014). *Halliday’s Introduction to Functional Grammar*. London: Routledge.
- Hiltunen, R. (1990). *Chapters on Legal English: Aspects, Past and Present of the Language of the Law*. Helsinki: Suomalaisen Tiedeakatemia Toimituksia.
- IIDEA, I. I. (2014). *What is a Constitution?* <http://www.iidea.int/publications/pgcb/index.cfm>: Retrieved, January 12, 2016.
- Ike, N. J. (2002). *English for specific purposes 1*. Abuja: Wildbest Educational Publishers.
- Irmawati, N. D., & Hum, M. (2014). Structural Linguistics and its Implication to Language Teaching. *International Journal on Studeis in English Language and Literature, Vol. 2*(8), 116-130.
- Khan, R., & Khan, S. (2015). Stylistic Study of Legal Language. *International Journal of Engineering Research and General Science, Vol. 3*(1), 2091-2730.

- Lutz, D. (2006). *Principles of Constitutional Design*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Mala, M. (2011). *Sentence Complexity in Academic Written English: A Syntactic Study with a Diachronic Perspective (1904 – 2005)*. LAT: Lambert Academic Publishing.
- Mala, M. (2012). Change in Syntactic Functions of Finite/Non-Finite Clauses in Newspaper Language: Similarities and Differences between Academic Prose and Newspaper Language. *BAS Journal*, 243-252.
- Mellinkoff, D. (1963). *The Language of the Law*. Boston: Little, Brown and Company.
- Ochs, E. (1979). Syntax and Semantics. In T. Givon, *Planned and Unplanned Discourse: Discourse and Syntax* (pp. 51-78). New York: Academic Press.
- Panther, K.-U., & Kopcke, K.-M. (2008). A Prototype Approach to Sentences and Sentences types. *Annual Review of Cognitive Linguistics*, 83-112.
- Payne, T. (2011). *Understanding English Grammar*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Phakiti, A. (2014). *Experimental Research Methods in Language Learning*. New York: Bloomsbury Academic.
- Post, R. (1990). Theories of Constitutional Interpretation. *Representations*, 30, 13-41.
- Quirk, R., Greenbaum, S., Leech, G., & Svartvik, J. (1985). *Comprehensive Grammar of the English Language*. Edinburgh: Longman Group Limited.
- Rozakis, L. (2003). *English Grammar for the Utterly Confused*. USA: McGraw-Hill.
- Schauer, F. (1982). An Essay on Constitutional Language. *Faculty Publication*, 797-832.
- Shitu, F. (2011). The Nature and Complexity of the Legal Document from the Perspective of Some Educated 'Laymen' in Federal College of Education, Abuja. *Journal of the Nigerian English Studies Association (JNESA)*, Vol. 14(2), 69-77.
- Thompson, G. (2014). *Introducing Functional Grammar*. London: Routledge.
- Tiersma, P. (1999). *Legal Language*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Ufot, B. G. (2013). Stylistics and ESP: A Lexico-Grammatical Study of Legal Discourse. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, Vol. 3(No. 4), 620-631.
- Vystrcilova, R. (2000). Legal Language. *Philosophica*, Vol. 73, 91-96.
- Wiredu, J. (2012). A Grammar of Newspaper Editorial Language: The Complex Sentence. *Legon Journal of the Humanities*, Vol23, 75-124.
- Wiredu, J. (2014). The Complex Sentence in Legal English: A Study of Law Reports. *Journal of Literature, Languages and Linguistics*, Vol. 22, 29-41.
- Wydict, R. (1998). *Plain English for Lawyers*. Durham, North Carolina: Carolina Academic Press.